

COMPARISON OF FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH BEHAVIOR OF THIN AND THICK ALUMINUM PLATE WITH COMPOSITE PATCH REPAIR

Dae-Cheol Seo, Jung-Ju Lee* and Tae Sung Jang

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology,
373-1, Kusong-dong, Yuseong-gu, Taejeon, 305-701, Korea*

SUMMARY: Fatigue crack growth behaviors of cracked aluminum plate with bonded composite patch were investigated through experimental and numerical study. Experiments involved fatigue tests of 2, 6, 10 mm thick specimens with edge crack repaired with unidirectional graphite/epoxy patch. Two types of patch configuration were used, i.e. constant thickness patch and constant stiffness ratio patch. The fatigue crack growth and fatigue life of thin and thick plate were compared. The $da/dN - \Delta K$ curves of SENT specimens repaired with bonded composite patch were obtained through fatigue tests. The stress intensity factor of patched crack was determined from experimental result by comparing the crack growth behavior of specimens with and without repair. Also, 3-D finite element analysis which model the non-uniform crack growth through the thickness direction were performed. The stress intensity factor calculated using FEM were compared with the experimentally determined values.

KEYWORDS: Composite Patch Repair, Fatigue, Thick plate patch

1. INTRODUCTION

The traditional repair method for cracked aircraft structure is fastening metal reinforcement using bolt and rivet. This method made worse the stress concentration problem due to drilling of additional fastener hole. Also the application of metal reinforcement change the stress distribution of repair area and cause the stress concentration along the neighborhood of repair. But, the adhesively bonded composite repairs cause minimum stress concentration and alter the load path that induce efficient load transfer from cracked structure to reinforcement. Thus, the reduction of stress intensity factor caused by bonded patch repair prevent or retard crack re-initiation or further growth. Improvements in durability and damage tolerance have been also demonstrated through this technology.

Several studies involving both experimental and analytical techniques have investigated the mechanics of bonded composite repairs on cracked thin metallic structures of about 3 mm or less thickness[1-4]. Repairs of thick plates have also been investigated, both numerically and experimentally, but in a limited amount[5-6]. The few experiments, performed in this area, showed the difference in crack growth rates between the repaired thin and thick components[7]. Further, experiments with thick panels have neglected bending effects due to

* : to whom all correspondence should be addressed. E-mail: jjlee@sorak.kaist.ac.kr

asymmetric repair or attempted to restrict bending by applying stiffeners to the specimens[5-6]. Recently, Schubbe and Mall[8] investigated the fatigue crack growth rate of thick panels under different patch configuration. They also developed finite element analysis involving three-layers of two-dimensional Mindlin plate elements to characterize fatigue crack growth behavior of a thick metallic panel repaired with an adhesively bonded composite patch[9]. Jones and Chiu[10] investigated a series of experimental and numerical studies into the repair of cracks in thick structural components.

In this study, we investigated the fatigue crack growth behavior of cracked aluminum plate with bonded composite patch repair especially in thick plate. Adhesively bonded composite patch repair technique has been expanded its application to load bearing primary structure repair from secondary structure repair. So a thorough understanding of crack growth behavior of thick panel repaired with bonded composite patch is needed. So, in this study, we examined the fatigue crack growth behavior of thin and thick panel repaired with bonded composite patch. In fatigue crack growth behavior, the relationship between stress intensity factor range(ΔK) and fatigue crack growth rate (da/dN) suggested by Paris was proven its usefulness by many researchers. So, in this study, we investigated the fatigue crack growth behavior of thin and thick panel repaired with bonded composite patch using the stress intensity factor range and fatigue crack growth rate. Also, by considering the three-dimensional stress state of patch crack, three dimensional finite element analyses were performed to obtain the stress intensity factor of crack repaired by bonded composite patch.

2. EXPERIMENTALS

Specimens were machined from aluminum sheet(Al 7075T6). Specimens were 220 mm long x 70 mm wide SENT(single edge notched tension) specimen as shown in Fig. 1. Specimen thickness was varied as 2, 6, 10 mm to examine the patch effectiveness under varying specimen thickness. A electric-discharge machined(EDM) starter notch was nominally 7 mm long which was then pre-cracked to 10 mm length before repairing with graphite/epoxy patch.

Two types of patch configuration were used, i.e. constant thickness patch and constant stiffness ratio patch. The patch thickness was 1 mm in constant patch thickness test and varied to maintain stiffness ratio($S=E_r t_r/E_p t_p$) equal to 1 in constant stiffness ratio test. The different patch thickness was chosen to examine the effect of patch thickness on patch effectiveness in thin and thick plate. The aluminum plate and composite patch surface were treated using sand papers and bonded using epoxy adhesive(Dexter-Hysol 9460). The adhesive were cured for 3 days in room temperature condition by following manufacturer's recommendation. The room temperature curing is selected to remove the bending effect caused by thermal residual stress caused by thermal mismatches between aluminum and graphite/epoxy during normal high temperature curing.

Fatigue tests were performed using a servo-hydraulic testing machine. The test frequency was 11 Hz and it is reduced to 2 Hz when measuring the crack length. A stress ratio of $R=0.1$ and maximum stress of 35 MPa sinusoidal waveform was used to fatigue specimens. Load and displacement signal were obtained using a PC with data acquisition system.

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

In patch repair of thin plate, there is small crack front growth variation in thickness direction. But in thick plate repaired with bonded patch, there is a considerable crack front growth variation between patched and unpatched side as shown in Fig. 2. This is because stress intensity factor variation in thickness direction is more severe than that of thin plate. In analyses of composite patch repair of thin plate, many researchers ignore crack growth difference between patched and unpatched side, but in analysis of composite patch repair of thick plate, the crack growth difference between patched and unpatched side should be regarded. The crack growth difference between patched and unpatched side is about 10 mm at 35 mm crack length. Crack growth difference at other crack length is assumed as linearly varied from 0 to 10 mm. The experimental crack front is in elliptic shape, but in FEM modeling, crack front is modeled as linear shape for simplicity. 20 node isoparametric brick elements were used and the quarter-point crack tip singular elements were used to model crack tip area. Analyses were performed at 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35 mm crack length to calculate the stress intensity factor as a function of crack length. Due to symmetry, only a half area of the plate was analyzed.

The stress distributions(σ_y) obtained by finite element analysis were shown in Fig. 3. The stress near the crack was considerably reduced by patch effect as shown in Fig. 3. The reduced stress also caused the reduction of stress intensity factor. The stress intensity factor showed a 50% reduction at mid-plane, but showed only a small reduction at unpatched free surface. The difference of stress intensity factor reduction between patched and unpatched side was become considerable as the specimen thickness was increased. This is because the restrained area by patch effect in thick plate is smaller than that of thin plate. So the reduction of stress intensity factor is also small in thick plate.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Base specimen test result

To obtain the base fatigue crack growth behavior of aluminum plate before composite patch repair, fatigue tests of SENT specimen were performed. Fatigue tests were performed in two load levels. One is high stress level(35MPa) which is equal to the stress level of patched specimen test and other is low stress level(17.5MPa) to obtain base fatigue crack growth data. Fatigue crack growth rate was about 10^{-7} ~ 10^{-6} m/cycle in the case of high stress level(35MPa) and was about 10^{-8} ~ 10^{-7} m/cycle in the case of low stress level(17.5MPa). The fatigue crack growth rate of the base specimen tested at the low stress level showed a similar range to that of the patched specimen tested at the high stress level. The crack length-cycle($a-N$) curves of the base specimen were shown in Fig. 4. The crack growth of 10 mm thick specimen was faster than that of 2 mm thick specimen as the crack growth of plain strain condition is faster than that of plain stress state. The crack growth rate was calculated using 7 point incremental polynomial method suggested in ASTM Standard E-647. Stress intensity factor, K , was calculated using the equation for a through crack of SENT specimen shown as follows.

$$K = \frac{P}{B\sqrt{W}} f\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) = \frac{P}{B\sqrt{W}} \frac{\sqrt{2 \tan\left(\frac{pa}{2w}\right)}}{\cos\left(\frac{pa}{2w}\right)} \left[0.752 + 2.02\left(\frac{a}{w}\right) + 0.37\left(1 - \sin\left(\frac{pa}{2w}\right)\right)^3 \right] \quad (2)$$

4.2 Calculation of SIF from experimental results

Two types of composite patch were used for three thickness (2, 6, 10 mm) specimens tested in this experiment. One is the ‘thin’ patch which has the same 1 mm thickness and other is the ‘thick’ patch which has the same stiffness ratio. As the effect of composite patch acts as a reduction of stress intensity factor, the fatigue crack growth behavior of aluminum plate itself is the same in specimens with and without composite patch repair. So, the stress intensity factor of patched crack can be determined from experimental results by comparing the fatigue crack growth behavior of the base specimen and composite patch repaired specimen.. The

Paris law of crack propagation, i.e. $da/dN = C(\Delta K)^m$, was used to study the fatigue behaviors of cracked aluminum specimens with and without repairs. It would be assumed that the value of material constants C and m remains unchanged for the fatigue analysis of the cracked specimens with or without repairs as the effect of patch repair acts as a reduction of stress intensity factor. So, the DK of patch repaired specimen can be determined experimentally from the crack growth rate, da/dN , data and the stress intensity factor of cracked specimen without repair.

To verify the validity of experimentally determined stress intensity factors of patch repaired specimens, they were compared with the stress intensity factors calculated using FEM. To evaluate the stress intensity calculated using FEM, it is needed to define a average stress intensity factor, ΔK_{avg} , that lie between the two values. Here, we defined the average stress intensity, ΔK_{avg} , by averaging all values calculated at all element located between the mid-plane and the unpatched side. The ΔK_{exp} determined from experimental results and the ΔK_{avg} calculated using FEM were compared and shown in Fig. 5. The ΔK_{avg} showed slightly larger values than the ΔK_{exp} , but overall trend were coincide.

4.3 Fatigue crack growth behavior of patch repaired specimen

To investigate the effect of specimen thickness, 2, 6, 10 mm thick specimens repaired with the same 1 mm thickness composite patch are fatigue tested. The stiffness ratios were 1., 0.33, 0.2, respectively. The crack length vs. fatigue cycle curves were shown in Fig. 6. The 2 mm thick specimen which has the highest stiffness ratio showed the longest fatigue life and the slowest crack growth. The da/dN - DK curves were shown in Fig. 7. Here, the average stress intensity factor, ΔK_{avg} , were used for the stress intensity factor of patch repaired specimen.

Specimens repaired with patch which has the same stiffness ratio were tested to verify the effect of the stiffness ratio. When the stiffness ratio is set to unity, thickness of composite patch for 2, 6, 10 mm thick specimens were 1.03, 3.09, 5.15 mm, respectively and the number of ply were 8, 24, 40 ply, respectively. The a - N for each specimens were shown in Fig. 8. The fatigue life was increased than that of specimens repaired with the same 1 mm thickness patch shown in Fig. 6. The fatigue life of 10 mm thick specimen increased about two times and that of 6 mm thick specimen increased about three times compared to those of specimens repaired with 1 mm thickness patch, respectively. Though, the stiffness ratio which

is the most important parameter in representing the effect of composite patch repair is the same, thin(2mm) specimens showed longer fatigue life than thick(6, 10 mm) specimens. This is because the difference of stress distribution between patched and unpatched side increases and the reduction of stress intensity factor at unpatched side decreases as the thickness of specimens increases. As the thickness of specimen increased, the thickness of patch also increased to maintain the stiffness ratio. This increase in patch thickness cause more shift in neutral axis of patched specimen due to asymmetric patch. The shift of neutral axis causes bending of specimen. This bending acts as opening the crack and increases the stress intensity factor of patched specimen, so, acts as a detrimental effect on crack growth behavior. The da/dN - DK curves of crack specimens repaired with the same stiffness ratio were shown in Fig. 9.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue crack growth behaviors of cracked plate with bonded composite patch were investigated through experimental and numerical study. Experiments involved fatigue tests of 2, 6, 10 mm thick specimens with edge crack repaired with unidirectional graphite/epoxy patch. The fatigue crack growth and fatigue life of thin and thick plate were compared. The stress intensity factor of patched crack was determined from experimental result by comparing the crack growth behavior of specimens with and without repair. Also, 3-D finite element analyses, which model the non-uniform crack growth through the thickness direction, were performed. The stress intensity factor calculated using FEM were compared with the experimentally determined values. The following conclusions can be drawn from this study.

1. The fatigue crack growth behavior of thin and thick specimens repaired with bonded composite patch showed differences in both fatigue life and crack front growth. The thick specimen showed non-uniform crack front growth and showed less fatigue life than thin specimen repaired with bonded composite patch which has the same stiffness ratio.
2. 3-D Finite element analyses which model the non-uniform crack front growth behavior of thick specimen repaired with bonded composite patch were performed. The stress intensity factor of thick specimen showed a large variation through thickness direction. The average stress intensity factor was proposed by averaging the values from mid-plane to unpatched side and show a good agreement in comparing with experimentally determined values.
3. The da/dN – DK curves of SENT specimens repaired with bonded composite patch were obtained through fatigue tests. The stress intensity factors of patched crack were determined from the experimental result and compared with the calculated values using FEM.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, AA and Jones, R. (1988) "Bonded Repair of Aircraft Structures," Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.
2. Baker, A.A., (1993) "Repair Efficiency in Fatigue Cracked Aluminum Components Reinforced with Boron/Epoxy Patches." Fatigue and Fracture for Engineering Material

and structure, Vol.16, 753-765.

3. Denney J.J., Mall S., (1997) "Characterization of Disbond Effects on Fatigue Crack Growth Behavior in Aluminum Plate with Bonded Composite Patch," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.57, no.5, 507-525.
4. Fredell, R.S., (1994) "Damage Tolerant Repair Techniques for Pressurized Aircraft Fuselages," Ph.D. Dissertation, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft Univ. of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands.
5. Kan H.P., Ratwani M.M., (1983) "Composite Patch Repair of Thick Aluminum Structures-Final Report," Airtask No.WF41-400, PE 62241, Report No. NADC-82139-60, United States Navy-Naval Air Development Center, Warminster, PA 18974.
6. Jones R., Moment L., Baker AA., Davis MJ., (1988) "Bonded Repair of Metallic Components: Thick Sections," *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.9, 61-70.
7. Labor, J.D. and Ratwani, M.M., (1980) "Development of bonded composite patch repairs for cracked metal structure-final report", Report No. NADC79066-60. Vol. 1, United States Navy-Naval Air Development Center. Warminster, PA 18974.
8. Schubbe, J.J. and Mall, S., (1999) "Investigation of a cracked thick aluminum panel repaired with a bonded composite patch", *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 63, 305-323.
9. Schubbe, J.J. and Mall, S., (1999) "Modeling of cracked thick metallic structure with bonded composite patch repair using three-layer technique", *Composite Structures*, Vol., 45, 185-193.
10. Jones, R. and Chui, W.K., (1999) "Composite repairs to cracks in thick metallic components", *Composite Structures*, Vol., 44, 17-29.

Fig. 1 Patched SENT specimen(dimensions : mm).

Fig.2 cross section of test specimen

(a) unpatched (b) patched
Fig. 3 Stress(σ_y) distribution of (a) unpatched (b) patched cracked aluminum plate.

Fig. 4 Fatigue crack growth of base specimen as a function of cycle.

(a) thin patch

(b) thick patch)

Fig. 5 Comparison of ΔK calculated from experimental results(ΔK_{exp}) and averaged FEM results(ΔK_{avg}).

Fig. 6 Fatigue crack growth of patched specimen as a function of cycle.

Fig. 9 Fatigue crack growth of thick patched specimen as a function of ΔK .

Fig. 7 Fatigue crack growth rate of patched specimen as a function of ΔK .

Fig. 8 Fatigue crack growth of thick patched specimen as a function of cycle.